

STUDY OF ANATOMICAL STRUCTURE OF LEAF DIOSCOREA NIPPONICA
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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada *Dioscorea nipponica* turini bargining anatomik tuzilishi, har bir to'qimaning joylashishi, tuzilishi va vazifalari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari *D. nipponica* turlarining anatomik tuzilishiga asoslangan taksonomiyasiga yordam beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot *Dioscorea nipponica* barglari eudicot o'simlikiga o'xshash xususiyatlarga ega ekanligini aniqladi. Hozirgi kuzatishlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, *Dioscorea nipponica* yuzasi bitta trixomalar bilan qoplangan. Tomirlar to'plamining tuzilishi metaksilema tomirlari, traxeidlar va floema birliklarining V shaklidagi yakuniy joylashuvi bilan ifodalanadi. Raphid kristallari barg mezofilli to'qimalarida mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: yams, *Dioscorea*, bargi, epiderma, kutikula, palisada, o'tkazuvchi boylam.

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация об анатомическом строении листа *Dioscorea nipponica*, расположении, строение и функциях каждой ткани. Результаты исследования вносят вклад в таксономию видов *D. nipponica* на основе их анатомической структуры. Это исследование показало, что листья *Dioscorea nipponica* имели сходные черты с эвдикотовым растением. Настоящие наблюдения показали, что поверхность *Dioscorea nipponica* была покрыта единичными трихомами. Структура сосудистого пучка представлена V-образным завершающим расположением сосудов метаксилемы, трахеид и единиц флоэмы. В ткани мезофилла листа присутствовали рафидные кристаллы.

Ключевые слова: батат, *Dioscorea*, лист, эпидерма, кутикула, палисада, проводящий слой.

Abstract. This article provides information about the anatomical structure of the *Dioscorea nipponica* leaf, the location, structures and functions of each tissue. Results of this study will contribute to the taxonomy of *D. nipponica* species based on their anatomical structure. This study found that the leaves of *Dioscorea nipponica* had similar features to the eudicot plant. The present observations showed that the surface of *Dioscorea nipponica* was covered with single trichomes. The structure of the vascular bundle is represented by a V-shaped final arrangement of metaxylem vessels, tracheids and phloem units. Raphid crystals were present in the leaf mesophyll tissue.

Keywords: sweet potato, *Dioscorea*, leaf, epidermis, cuticle, palisade, conductive layer.

A leaf (Latin folium) is, in Botany, a vegetative organ of a plant whose main functions are photosynthesis, gas exchange and transpiration. For this purpose, the leaf usually has a lamellar structure to give cells containing the specialized pigment chlorophyll in the chloroplasts access to sunlight. The leaf is also the plant's organ of respiration, evaporation, and guttation (release of water droplets). Leaves can retain water and nutrients, and in some plants they have other functions [1].

Leaves were fixed in 70% ethyl alcohol according to a known technique and studied in transverse section in the fixed material (Trankowski, 1979). To study anatomical features of leaves, hand-cut preparations and a MOTIC V1 microscope were used.

The preparations were stained with safranin. Cell and tissue measurements were made using a MOB-15 micrometer. Numerous measurements of a number of seed characteristics were carried out according to the generally accepted methodology: seed coat height, ovary thickness, and endosperm thickness (Dospikhov, 1985). Statistical analysis of data was carried out using a personal computer (MS Excel) according to generally accepted methods. Microphotographs were performed with a digital camera, and mathematical analysis was studied under a MOTIC microscope.

The presence of bioactive compounds and microanatomy on leaves, stems and petioles of *Dioscorea species* (*Dioscorea alata* and *Dioscorea Bulbifera*) was studied [4]. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of saponins, tannins, glycosides and absence of alkaloids, anthraquinone and phlobatannin in *Dioscorea alata*. In *Dioscorea Bulbifera*, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, glycosides and flavonoids were present while anthraquinone and phlobatannin were absent. Microanatomical section of *Dioscorea alata* leaf showed amphistomatous epidermal cells with thickened cell wall and distinct medial lamina bounded by intercellular air space, adaxial epidermal cells with eccentric nuclei, large central vacuole with thin peripheral layer of cytoplasm. In the epidermis of *Dioscorea bulbifera* leaves, anamocytic and anisocytic stomata, as well as dense pilosebaceous trichomes with cuticular-stripped cell wall on the adaxial and abaxial epidermis were found. Histologic sections of *Dioscorea alata* stem revealed vascular bundles arranged in the form of two concentric circles. The vascular bundle of the outer circle was smaller than the inner circle, with two metaxylem vessels along with a single phloem unit at both ends, but slices of *Dioscorea bulbifera* stem showed inner circle bundles with unpaired metaxylem with a phloem unit at one end. Sections of the petiole of *Dioscorea alata* show predominantly collateral vascular bundles, located at one end of the petiole.

Features of leaf epidermis that revealed similarities between wild-type and micropropagated plants included amphistome state, presence of mucus, glandular unicellular trichomes with multicellular heads, polygonal cells with smooth walls, and type and shape of stomata. Minor variations included a thick cuticular wall with closed stomata in wild-type plants compared with thin-walled open stomata in in vitro plants. The opening of the stomata resulted in an increase in the average size of the stomata (7.68-0.38) μm and (6.14-0.46) μm on the adaxial side [5].

Examined under optical microscope, scanning electron microscope (SEM) and transmission electron microscope (TEM) for stem, leaf, petiole, tuber, root and flower of *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst. provided detailed information on the anatomical features that defined this species. The anatomical study showed that the leaves of *Dioscorea hispida* had similar features to eudicot plants, but the stem, tuber and flower resembled monocotyledonous plants. The leaf surface of *Dioscorea hispida* was covered with rough, bristly and spiny trichomes or hairy surface [6].

Structure of the leaf lamina of *Dioscorea nipponica* (1-drawing).

1-fig: General view of a transverse section of a *Dioscorea nipponica* Makino. leaf: PP- Conducting bundle, HE- upper epidermis, NE-lower epidermis, K-cuticle, SCL-sclerenchyma, KS-xylem, PL-palisade, CR- raphid crystals

The epidermis is a layer of cells that protects against harmful environmental influences and excessive water evaporation. The upper (adaxial) and lower (abaxial) epidermis have a single layer of cells, each covered by a cuticle. Often on top of the epidermis, the leaf is covered with a protective layer of waxy origin (cuticle). The stomata are restricted to the lower surface only (hypostomal). In the epidermis of *Dioscorea nipponica* leaves, anamocytic and anisocytic stomata, as well as single pilosebaceous trichomes with cuticular striated cell wall were found on the adaxial and abaxial epidermis. Also, raphide crystals are present in the epidermis.

The palisade (above, densely packed cells) and spongy (below, loosely packed cells) portions of the mesophyll, located between the upper and lower epidermal layers, are shown.

The mesophyll, or parenchyma, is the inner chlorophyll-bearing tissue that performs the main function, photosynthesis.

Network of veins formed by conducting bundles (conducting tissue) consisting of vessels and sieve-like tubes for the movement of water, dissolved salts, sugars and mechanical elements.

Stomata are special complexes of cells located mainly on the lower surface of leaves; they are used for evaporation of excess water (transpiration) and gas exchange.

Epiderma is the outer layer of a multilayered cell structure that covers the leaf from all sides; the boundary area between the leaf and the environment. The epidermis performs several important functions: it protects the leaf from excessive evaporation, regulates gas exchange with the environment, excretes metabolic substances and, in some cases, absorbs water. Most leaves have a dorsoventral anatomy: the upper and lower surfaces of the leaf have different structures and perform different functions.

The epidermis is usually transparent (there are no or few chloroplasts in its structure) and is covered on the outside by a protective layer of waxy origin (cuticle), which prevents evaporation. The cuticle on the lower part of the leaf is generally thinner than on the upper part, and thicker in biotopes with arid climates compared to those where there is no moisture deficit.

The epidermal tissue consists of the following cell types: epidermal (or motor) cells, defense cells, accessory cells, and trichomes. Epidermal cells are the most numerous, largest (11.2 ± 0.3 , 15.4 ± 0.4) and least adapted (9.1 ± 0.2 , 11.1 ± 0.4). The epidermis is covered with pores called stomata, which are part of a whole complex consisting of a pore surrounded on all sides by chloroplast-containing guard cells and two to four side cells lacking chloroplast.

This complex regulates evaporation and gas exchange of the leaf with the environment. As a rule, the number of stomata on the lower part of the leaf

Table. Quantitative parameters of *Dioscorea nipponica* leaf mesophyll

№	Signs	Indicators, microns
1	Length of the upper epidermis	11,2±0,3
2	Width of upper epidermis	9,1±0,2
3	Length of lower epidermis	15,4±0,4
4	Width of lower epidermis	11,1±0,4
5	Palisade length	13,2±0,4
6	Palisade width	10,1±0,2
7	Sclerenchyma length	12,2±0,4
8	Sclerenchyma width	11,3±0,2
9	Parenchyma length	14,5±0,4
10	Parenchyma width	13,3±0,3

Most of the leaf interior between the upper and lower layers of the epidermis is parenchyma (the main tissue), or mesophyll. Normally, the mesophyll is formed by chlorophyll-synthesizing cells, so the synonymous name chlororenchyma is also used. The product of photosynthesis is called photosynthate.

Leaves are usually colored green due to chlorophyll, a photosynthetic pigment found in chloroplasts, the green plastids. Plants lacking or lacking chlorophyll cannot photosynthesize.

The leaf veins are vascular tissue and are located in the spongy layer of mesophyll. The veins consist of xylem, the tissue used to conduct water and dissolved minerals, and phloem, the tissue used to conduct organic matter synthesized by the leaves. Usually the xylem lies on top of the phloem. Together they form the main tissue called the leaf core.

The lamina has 3-4 protruding veins running from the base to the apex. The cuticle of the lamina is optically thickened. The leaf has a layered epidermis, the soptic wall on the abaxial cells is convoluted and the adaxial cells have a straight wall. Stomata with irregular distribution and anomocytic type are found on the abaxial surface. Palisade tissue was clearly distinguished, elongated, compactly arranged and oriented vertically, with a transverse section on the adaxial side (13.2±0.4, 10.1±0.2), and spongy tissue was arranged either loosely or compactly with irregularly sized cells.

Information on the anatomical characters of *Dioscorea* was described by Ayensu (1972), which has already provided a more complete picture of the taxonomic status of this genus. The results of this study will contribute to the taxonomy of *D. nipponica* species based on their anatomical structure. This study showed that the leaves of *Dioscorea nipponica* had similar features to the eudicot plant. The present observations showed that the surface of *Dioscorea nipponica* was covered with single trichomes. The structure of the vascular bundle was represented by a V-shaped terminating arrangement of metaxylem vessels, tracheids and phloem units. Rafide crystals were present in the leaf mesophyll tissue.

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